

Upright growth with fewer, well-spaced, thick, not-too-short, and stiff leaves should improve penetration of solar radiation as well as free movement of air through the stand. At a constant leaf area index, leaves of taller plants would be spaced farther apart than those of dwarf plants, which should considerably neutralize negative effects of tall stature on sunlight penetration through the canopy. Tall erect rice cultivars are likely to also have deeper roots, to better absorb water and nutrients.

Identification of these morphological traits allows construction of a basic ideotype with characteristic features of taller stature; lodging resistance; upright growth; fewer, all effective tillers; fewer, well-spaced, thick, not-too-short, stiff leaves; heavy panicles; limited intraplant variation in panicle yield; and deep, extensively branched roots. Cultivars of this type would have to be grown at closer spacing.

Rewa 353 (PAU125-1-2/Lalco 14) is our first prototype. It is 130 cm tall, with an average of six very upright, stiff tillers (all effective)/ plant. Highly synchronous panicles yield an average 4 g of long, slender grains. It has <10% sterility and a harvest index of 0.50.

In 1982, Rewa 353 averaged a yield of 4.3 t/ha over 19 locations, compared with 3.85 t/ha for semidwarf check Rasi. In 1983, average yields over 23 locations were 3.5 for Rewa 353 and 2.8 t/ha for Rasi. Both cultivars flower in about 85 d. Although Rewa 353 is an inadequate approximation of the new ideotype, its performance in wider spacings than ideal shows merit. □

Tolerance of 100 indica rice varieties for 2 herbicides. Hangzhou, China.

Reaction ^a	Butachlor	Thiobencarb
Highly tolerant	Long-jiang-dao Radiation 8-1	Long-jiang-dao Wu-jie-gu
Tolerant	B-8 Pioneer 1, Zhen-long 13, Ai-jiao-nan-te, Radiation 85-65, Wu-jie-gu, Xiao-hong-gu, Min-shang 1	B-8 Er-jiu-nan 1, 82-469
Medium tolerant	Er-jiu-lu 1, Ai-nan-zao 1, Ai-nan-zao 39, Lu-hong-zao 1, Tie-lu 17, Xiang-zhu 443 Zhong 834, Zuo 5, Zao-xian 141, 3168-3, Wen 189, Er-jiu-nan 1, 82-469, Qing-lian 16, Wen-ge, IR58, Zhe-fu 802, E-zao 6, Long-fei 313, Er-jiu-ai 7, 60-ri-zao, 70-ri-huo-dao, Qing-gu-ai, Conggui 3, Yin-bu-ai	Er-jiu-lu 1, Ai-nan-zao 1, Ai-nan-zao 39, Lu-hong-zao 1, Tie-lu 17, Xiang-zhu 443 Radiation 8-1, Pioneer 1, Zhen- long 13, Radiation 85-65, Min- shang 1, IR1710
Susceptible	Zhen-shan 97, Si-mei 2, Guang-lu-ai 4, Er-jiu-qing, Zao-jian 1, Jia-xian 785, Zhong 86-151, Gui-lu-ai 8, Wen-guang-qing, Qing-gan-huang, Zhu-xi 26, Nong 8506, Ai-chang 25, PL 15, 15-4, Zhu-yun-nuo, Zao-xian 503, Lian-tang-zao, Zao-lian 31, Xiang-zao-xian 3, Radiation 83-29, BG 367-7, IR54, Dong-hai 109, Tetep, Cong-gui 314, Guang-liu-zao Bao-nan-zao, IR29, Qing-xiao-jin-zao, Zhong 84-86, Zhen-gui 51, Yuan-feng-zao, Er-jiu-feng, Zao-er-liu 14, Chuan 84-508, Shu-feng 1, Zhen-lu-xi 1, Cong-xie 39, Guang-er-ai 105, Guang-hong 40, IR22, IR22107, IR1710	Zhen-shan 97, Si-mei 2, Guang- lu-ai 4, Er-jiu-qing, Zao-jian 1, Jia-xian 785, Zhong 86-151, Gui-lu-ai 8, Wen-guang-qing, Qing-gan-huang, Zhu-xi 26, Nong 8506, Ai-chang 25, PL 15, 15-4, Zhu-yun-nuo, Zao-xian 503, Lian-tang-zao, Zao-lian 31, Xiang-zao-xian 3, Radiation 83- 29, BG 367-7, IR54, Dong-hai 109, Tetep, Cong-gui 314, Guang-liu-zao Ai-jiao-nan-te, Zhong 83-4, Zuo 5, 3168-3, Wen 189, Qing-lian 16, E-zao 6, Long-fei 313, Er-jiu-ai 7, 70-ri-huo-dao, Qing- gu-ai, Cong-gui 3, Yin-bu-ai, Zao-feng-shou, Yin-zao 41 1, Zhu-ke 2, Hong 410, IR26
Highly susceptible	Fu-yu 1, Zhe 85-2, Wen-xuan-qing, L201, L202, IR24, IR30, 5010, Zhu-lian-ai, B3, IR50, Yuan-wu, Chun- feng 1, Zhai-ye-qing 8, IR9129, Hua-ai 837 Zao-feng-shou, Yin-zao 411, Zhu-ke 2, Hong 410, IR26	Fu-yu 1, Zhe 85-2, Wen-xuan- qing, L201, L202, IR24, IR30, 5010, Zhu-lian-ai, B3, IR50, Yuan-wu, Chun-feng 1, Zhai-ye- qing 8, IR9129, Hua-ai 837 Xiao-hong-gu, Zao-xian 141, Wen-ge, IR58, Zhe-fu 802, 60-ri-zao, Bao-nan-zao, IR29, Qing-xiao-jin-zao, Zhong 84-86, Zhen-gui 51, Yuan-feng-zao, Er-jiu-feng, Zao-er-liu 14, Chuan 84-508, Shu-feng 1, Zhen-lu-xi 1, Cong-xie 39, Guanger-ai 105, Guang-hong 40, IR22, IR22107

^aHighly tolerant: 2d and 3d leaves normal; tolerant: 2d leaf partially with water-soaked light brown spots, 3d normal; medium tolerant: 2d leaf with many large light brown spots, 3d with some; susceptible: spots linked with each other, leaves partially necrotic; highly susceptible: seedlings nearly dead or dead.

A technique for screening herbicide tolerance in rice

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We developed a technique to evaluate indica rices for herbicide tolerance at the seedling stage. To speed up screening for herbicide tolerance, we used the

treatment method commonly applied in the field on seedlings in the incubator.

Seedlings were grown in 50- × 20- × 15-cm plastic trays with 7-cm-deep soil. At the 2-leaf stage, different trays were flooded with 50, 100, and 500 ppm butachlor, and 250, 500, and 1,000 ppm thiobencarb up to the pulvinus of the second leaf, with water treatment as a

check. Seedlings were kept in the incubator (30/25 °C day/night, 12 h light and 3000 lx/d) for 11 d.

Treatment with 100 ppm butachlor or 500 ppm thiobencarb was best for discriminating herbicide tolerance among varieties. In most varieties, tolerance for both herbicides was similar (correlation coefficient 0.67**).

The 100 varieties screened could be divided into five response groups (see table). Long-jiang-ao, Radiation 8-1, B-8, and Pioneer 1 were tolerant of butachlor; Long-jiang-dao, B-8, Wu-jie gu, and Er-jiu-nan 1 were tolerant of thiobencarb. IR30, IR54, and Fu-yu 1 were susceptible to both herbicides. □

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Grain quality and nutritional value

Induced variation in aromatic rice cultivars

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Traditional aromatic varieties Karnal Local and Bindli were irradiated with 30 kR gamma rays to obtain semidwarf, nonlodging mutants that retain parental cooking quality characteristics. Only morphological mutants were selected and grown to the M₅ generation.

Important agronomic traits were recorded on five randomly selected plants per mutant. Bulk milled rice samples were used for grain quality analysis.

All short-statured mutants selected from Karnal Local tend to lodge and are near or inferior to the parent in yield per plant (see table). Mutants KLM-14 and KLM-24 possess longer and finer grains with desirable alkali spreading value and amylose content. Except for Karnal Local Mutant-8 (nonaromatic), all mutants have strong aroma.

All mutants selected from Bindli are strongly aromatic. Mutants below 100

cm height have thick, sturdy stems and relatively upright, dark green leaves. Bindli Mutants (BM) 34, 65, and 68 have desirable alkali spreading value and amylose content. BM64 is taller than its parent.

Early-maturing aromatic strains, whether land races or developed through recombination breeding/mutation, that flower and mature at higher temperature and relatively high humidity do not develop aroma or develop only mild aroma. BM21 and BM24, despite having very short durations, maintained strong aroma and parental level of amylose content and alkali spreading value when they flowered and matured in Sep in North India. □

Range and mean for induced variations.

Character	Karnal Local	24 mutants of Karnal Local			Bindli	23 mutants of Bindli		
		Range	Mean ^a	SD		Range	Mean ^a	SD
Plant height (cm)	135.60	76.00-134.40	104.53	15.35	146.40	86.80-172.10	101.04	21.65
Tillers (no./plant)	15.00	10.00- 22.00	15.00	3.18	13.00	6.00- 17.00	12.12	2.60
Yield (g/plant)	29.30	4.50- 29.30	20.17	5.85	20.84	5.62- 37.14	21.19	7.85
Test grain weight ^b (g)	23.00	17.00- 25.80	21.10	2.31	18.00	10.50- 20.00	18.07	2.24
Filled grains (no./panicle)	85.00	20.00-103.00	65.72	20.33	80.00	57.00- 140.00	94.58	20.36
Duration (d)	150.00	132.00-164.00	152.64	10.88	161.00	110.00- 166.00	156.60	15.00
Length (L) of milled rice (mm)	7.55	6.95- 8.88	7.62	0.47	4.77	3.22- 4.80	4.56	0.36
Breadth (B) of milled rice (mm)	1.78	1.40- 2.23	1.82	0.18	2.58	2.20- 2.68	2.52	0.12
L/B ratio	4.24	3.37- 5.80	4.22	0.64	1.85	1.74- 1.92	1.80	0.09
Alkali spreading value	3.00	3.00- 4.00	3.56	0.50	4.00	3.00- 4.00	3.78	0.41
Amylose content (%)	25.5	17.00- 29.50	24.02	4.02	27.00	23.00- 29.00	25.16	1.28

^aIncludes parent. ^bOne thousand randomly selected grains used to compute test grain weight.

Hua-03 — a high-protein indica rice

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Hua-03 is a newly released high-protein, early indica variety with wide

Table 1. Some agronomic characteristics and protein content of Hua-03. ^a Wuhan, China, 1983-88.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Protein content (% dry wt brown rice)
Hua-03	113	76.96	568.13	54.20	25.20	7.0	13.72
Guang-Lu-Ai 4	117	63.31	511.21	53.16	25.18	6.2	10.50

^aMean of 5 sites.